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HISTORICAL AND DEMOGRAPHIC VIEWS ON ENVIRONMENTAL, NATURAL- GEOGRAPHICAL AND POPULATION SETTLEMENT ISSUES IN THE WORKS OF NIZAMI GANJAVI

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Abstract

Human values, ideas of humanism, which still remain relevant today, found their new, eternal celebration in the work of the 12th century Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi. N. Ganjavi, who put forward extremely advanced ideas with his creativity, also touched on problems of great interest from a scientific point of view, related to the environment, natural-geographical factors and their impact on population growth and settlement. The genius poet was able to masterfully describe in his works the amazing features of geographical zones that differ sharply from each other in terms of their natural conditions. According to him, a person should be able to find ways to settle in all kinds of difficult and unfavorable natural areas. Therefore, in the works of Nizami Ganjavi, the issues of environment, natural-geographical factors and their impact on population settlement are extremely relevant and modern.

Keywords: Nizami Ganjavi, environmental issues, natural-geographical factors, settlement of population, historical demography.

Main

Favorable factors must first exist for the creation, development and settlement of every living thing, including the human race, on the planet Earth. The genius Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi knew the objective regularities of the planet we live in, the development dynamics of the events and processes taking place in the surrounding world, their natural causes, and their consequences for human society to an amazing degree, and skillfully reflected all these issues in his works. For instance, Nizami Ganjavi often talks about the vital importance of water for human settlement in his works. According to him, no living thing can exist or live normally in a place where plants do not grow. In the opinion of the genius poet, it is extremely important for people to settle in areas, where flora and fauna are in a normal state. For the existence of flora and fauna, the presence of water is the first, undeniable and necessary condition. Indeed, water preserves the vegetation on our planet, acts as the main component and factor that ensures its existence, and vegetation, in turn, preserves water and moisture. In modern times, ecological scientists rightly say: "If the earth is the mother, the water is the child, the forest will crack its lip without this child, and it will turn into a living dead" – they say.

It is interesting that Nizami Ganjavi in his famous "Khamsa" often describes his beloved heroes in areas where water is scarce and people suffer from thirst, that is, in the desert. Involuntarily, such a natural question arises. What is the reason for this? It can be assumed that in this way, the genius poet wanted to focus on the fact that his heroes have great will and thoughts, and that they can settle in unfavorable areas by fighting against the most cruel laws and difficulties of nature:

The liver was burning like hell.

*There was no cool water except the poison,
And besides the fire in the sun. – he writes. [2, p.413]*

While carefully reading the works of the great poet, you are amazed at how he describes the desert environment with amazing accuracy. In front of our eyes, it is as if the images in the research works of modern researchers about the desert come to life [9, pp. 143-165]. Nizami knows very well the natural characteristics of areas with low rainfall and high evaporation by the power of words. After all, in many areas of Azerbaijan where he lives, in the Kura-Araz and Devachi-Samur plains, in the sloping plains along Araz, including the Absheron peninsula, there is a semi-desert and dry steppe climate. If we consider that in the area where the poet lives - in the eastern part of the South Caucasus and in the low mountainous areas - there is a semi-desert and dry desert climate, then it becomes clear once again that Nizami Ganjavi has a high ability of observation and scientific analysis. But why does Nizami Ganjavi mostly use personage of Alexander the Great when describing natural zones that are less suitable for human habitation? According to Nizami Ganjavi, the most militant person is a knowledgeable and wise person. Nizami Ganjavi, who was well versed in Greek, Arabic and Indian philosophy, believed that the world consists of four main elements that smoothly complement each other. Elements of dialectics are characteristic of Nizami's outlook. Speaking about the change and movement of the world, Nizami notes in the poem "Khosrov and Shirin" that nothing in the world is permanent, just as water does not remain constant in the same stream [4, p. 121]. Without knowing the secrets of the world, how to fight it for a normal life? It also offers effective ways to combat thirst in water-scarce settlement areas. As interesting as it may seem, Nizami Ganjavi also describes the transfer of the liquid - water from the original source to the interior of the house, to the rooms. In the poem "Khosrov and Shirin", the poet says to Farhad, in the language of Shirin:

*He said: "Listen, O knowledgeable master!
Fulfill my wish, make me happy.
With your mastery, your capable hand,
Improve this castle, come listen to me.
We need milk, the herds are far away,
Find a solution for this in order to comfortable life" –
he appeals.*

Here, Shirin's appeal to Farhad to draw a canal of milk instead of water is surprising at first sight, of course, it evokes the impression of an impossible task. However, Shirin, who entrusted the execution of the work to Farhad, does not hesitate to share his suggestions and thoughts for the implementation of that project:

*"From here until we reach the herds,
If a strong ditch is dug out of stone,
Shepherds milk the milk in the pasture,
Servants drink it in the room". [2, pp. 148-149]*

In the given example, Shirin's idea of building a canal from stone for the optimal delivery of milk from a long distance to the place of residence is interesting. Because, precisely in a trench built with stone, it is possible to prevent the liquid from seeping into the soil unnecessarily, and therefore, from a large amount of loss. During the construction of the Karagum canal, which was intended to irrigate large cotton fields in the 20th century, one of the most important issues that scientists and engineers thought about was increasing the efficiency of this water plant. [7, p.188-189] Since this canal, which will be 1500 km long, is 10 times longer than the Suez Canal and 20 times longer than the Panama Canal, special purpose concrete material was planned for its floor (seat) and sides to prevent water loss. Apparently, we can clearly see the technology used in the construction of this water plant, which is called the construction of the century, in Nizami's work. On the other hand, if we take into account that the story of "Khosrov and Shirin" took place in a semi-desert, then we will witness that Nizami Ganjavi supported the idea of creating favorable conditions for life and habitation, which for settlement through the construction of reliable water facilities and canals from distant water sources to settlements.

Elsewhere, Nizami comes up with an effective proposal that is surprising in terms of modernity for obtaining high yields on unfit lands for cultivation. For example, in the poem "Treasure of Mysteries" in the chapter "Solomon and the sower", Prophet Solomon told the old man who was engaged in sowing and harvesting in salty soil: "If you don't find a drop of water, don't plant barley in salty soil. What did we get after sowing seeds in dry places? What we sowed was nothing, but we were left empty-handed" – he said, it is actually true from a scientific point of view. Because farming in saline and brackish soils is less efficient from an economic point of view. However, in the language of the old man, the poet addressing Solomon replied that if good seeds are sown in the soil, "700 grains will grow from one grain", in fact, he points to the existence of special types of spikes that are bred only for planting in sandy soils. And thus, it offers the most optimal way to get rid of the problem [5, pp. 47-48].

The genius poet describes Alexander the Great as an extremely intellectual and brave, invincible person. Therefore, Nizami speaks to the inhabitants of the populated areas with the language, intelligence and judgment of his beloved hero. Alexander does not spare his life and property while wandering through endless deserts:

*Abundant treasure he spent like sand,
He came back from the desert with pain. [3, p.552]*

In the words of the great poet, Alexander "passes like a storm through the terrible deserts that are on fire and speak to people with the language of fire". He is interested in the level of settlement in those places. In order to get to know the living conditions and livelihood of the people living in the desert, Kirdan met with the local population, who were also black, and asked them: "Does anyone or any living thing live in this desert besides you?" – he asks with a question. The local community complains that the living conditions in the place where they live are extremely harsh and difficult:

Here, Nizami skillfully describes the different landscape of two different settlements, which naturally stand out sharply from each other. Thus, Alexander considers it more appropriate to build new cities for residence in places with favorable water and other natural resources, not in arid steppes and deserts:

*When he reached a watery meadow,
He ordered, the stones are poured on the ground,
They built a big building from them. [3, p. 548]*

In his poem "Seven Beauties", Nizami clearly shows the praise of Simnar and the fact that during the construction of the Khavarnag fortress, Neman was looking for a convenient abode for himself before the construction works, in fact, he lists the important features of a normal settlement:

*They wandered every inch around,
Manzar and his father made a search,
Finally they found a good place.
Away from the heat, away from the sadness. [5, p. 97]*

However, in areas inhabited by people suffering from extreme heat, residential facilities consist of only simple and primitive buildings:

*These were the people of the field, were black,
Their living places were cave. [3, p. 555]*

Nizami Ganjavi says that it is not easy to live on the planet where we live without hard work and without facing difficulties. According to genius poet, a table is laid on the planet we live on. However, unfortunately along with the rich food and blessings of the Earth, there is also blood on this table:

*This place is a table with blood on it,
Besides these bloods, what does he have?*

Of course, when the great poet says blood, he means the merciless struggle and bloody wars waged by human generations for every inch of the planet we live on in order to settle in favorable areas:

...Where is an inch on this earth?

Don't let human blood be spilled there [5, p. 76]

Nizami Ganjavi points out with these lines that the lands suitable for life have been inhabited for a long time, and blood has been shed for every inch. According to the poet, the struggle for life and space exists not only among people, but among all living things. To

make this point, he emphasizes that even a delicate rose has its thorns:

*Tell him: "A rose is a thorn everywhere,
The place of the seal is the poisonous snake.*

It is for this reason that he calls the human race to settle not only in favorable areas, but also in areas where the natural possibilities for living are unfavorable, and for this to fight mercilessly with life:

Fight the world like a lion,

Otherwise, it will swallow you like a dragon.

Nizami Ganjavi sometimes "sends" his favorite hero, Alexander, to the dark country, sometimes to the waterless deserts, for the water of Life. Even though Alexander overcomes great difficulties and reaches that land, he does not get to drink the water of Life. Here, Nizami points out that death, like birth, is an objective demographic process. But did Alexander have to make the difficult journey to realize this simple truth? Nizami answers this question as follows:

*He is the smart person in the world,
He does not accept what he did not see with his
own eyes. [2, p. 548]*

In general, Nizami Ganjavi often refers to demographic processes such as population growth and decline in his other poems. The genius poet is not worried at all about the increase of people on earth. According to him, the Earth has enough necessary resources to support its inhabitants:

*Let him know that everyone eats bread,
As much as they eat from the storehouse of land,
Barley never runs out of his wealth.
O man, - harvester of barley,
You will give back to the world again.*

However, the abundance and inexhaustibility of the Earth's blessings does not mean that a person is comfortable. With the above verses, Nizami points out that the land that gave birth to a person will return him to itself again:

*Whoever comes to the world goodwill,
He will leave the world again.
Do not catch sturdy world for bread,
He killed many people like you.*

According to Nizami Ganjavi, neither a person's coming to this world nor his departure depends on his will, and everyone is an integral part not only of the world he lives in, but also of the infinite universe:

*In this blue sky, in this infinite universe
Everyone has their own place in life. [5, p. 48]*

Hence, a person is a humanistic and cosmic being. As big planets and bright stars in the universe, a person has its own place, its own position, its purpose is to settle the planet where it lives, to grow and reproduce. That is why, Nizami Ganjavi has great hope in the inexhaustible power and iron will of human. The poet believes that no obstacle can prevent a person who can do everything with his own hard work. A human is powerless only in the face of death:

*If there are a hundred mountains of steel, still believe,
A human can smash them into pieces.
A human is helpless only when,
There is no cure for death. [5, p.59]*

Nizami Ganjavi always keeps in mind that human life is as short as a few days and calls him not to waste his time, but to work actively:

*Let go of laziness, get a job, be diligent,
It's better if you train yourself a little. [5, p. 39]
Whoever said that pure emotion is born from man,
Human is always born from the soil*

It is for this reason that Nizami Ganjavi's heroes are not afraid of work, they do not shy away from their merciless struggle with slavery. Doesn't Farhad consider it an honor to stay in the desert to obtain Shirin's sympathy and love? Because he is too attached to his work, he likes to live in the desert:

*Don't talk about me going home, oh
... It is good that I live in this desert. [5, p. 91]*

That is why Nizami's hero Alexander travels around the world:

*Who once traveled the world?
How many countries did Alexander pass
through?*

*He came to his place, his homeland,
He shone his native land with light. [2, p. 522]*

In the scene of "Alexander's prophetic journey", Nizami Ganjavi describes the young conqueror's interesting dialogue with the people of the desert. Alexander asks the people of the desert, who are black from the scorching rays of the sun, whether other living beings live in this desert besides you, that is, the other people or animals? In other words, in the language of Alexander, Nizami expresses in the words of the people living in the desert under what conditions settlement can exist in unfavorable conditions:

*These deserts rarely see water and clouds,
We live in this waterless desert,
We eat the hunt of the desert,
...There is neither fire nor water here.
...These fiery deserts are horror, dread,
Not even a bird dares to fly [3, p. 555]*

Nizami Ganjavi also describes in an interesting way how the local people get water:

*When the dew falls and moistens the air,
We take water from the air with our breath. [3, p. 555]*

The inhabitants of the desert say with bitter regret that water is scarce and that they cannot take advantage of it as much as they would like:

*Water is poison to us, no one drinks water,
Air replaces water for us.*

Here, the genius poet Nizami Ganjavi, with great foresight, highlights how water is an invaluable resource, and the importance of treating it sparingly. Indeed, the shortage of water is clearly visible on the planet we live in today. Most of us have known since high school how vital water resources are to human settlement and existence on earth. It is true, at first glance, water seems to be everywhere. In particular, the abundance of blue shades, which indicate the presence of water on the globe, reinforces this idea in a person. In the poem of the "Seven Beauties", Nizami describes a careful attitude to even small rivers. According to Nizami, water and the conservation of fresh water resources of our planet is a vital factor. After all, out of every hundred liters of water, 97 liters of water are concentrated in the world's oceans and, due to their salinity,

are unfit for drinking, and only 3 liters are fresh water [8, pp. 22-23]. And of these 3 liters, 2 liters is in the glaciers of the Arctic and Antarctica liter [6, p. 189]. Thus, only 1 liter is fresh water. That is why Nizami writes:

*That spring, which sea the stream later spilled,
Kept like the apple of an eye, took care of it.*

It is also interesting that, in the poem of the “Seven Beauties”, an epic hero Bahram marries the daughters of the kings of 7 countries. However, Bahram does not make any difference between brides from different countries. He treats all women from various countries and continents with great respect. He highly appreciates the cultural values of each of them. This demonstrates how Nizami Ganjavi highly appreciated the equality of all races and peoples, as well as the multicultural values of mankind. Since, his hero Bahram Shah builds a luxurious palace for each of his wives. With these ideas, Nizami tries to convey the ideas of free marriage, regardless of religious and national differences between people. And each beauty from different countries tells the Shah her magic story. These seven stories constitute the content of Nizami’s poem. Nizami refers to our planet as a single home for all mankind. Therefore, natural factors for him are paramount issues. For Nizami,

the issues of fertility and resettlement should not violate the integrity of nature and the environment.

Thus, the genius Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi calls people to constantly travel and learn about the planet we live in, to explore its unknown secrets, to use natural resources sparingly and wisely, to acquire new and favorable areas for living as places of settlement.

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